

FORMATION OF INNOVATIVE COMPETENCE OF TEACHERS IN THE MANAGEMENT OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS.

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Annotation: This article highlights the theoretical and practical aspects of the process of forming the innovative competence of teachers in educational institutions. Methods for developing competencies based on innovative approaches, modern educational technologies, and foreign experience are analyzed.

Keywords: Innovation, competence, education management, pedagogical technology, modern education, foreign experience.

At the heart of the large-scale reforms being carried out in the education system of our country, special attention is paid to the training of highly qualified personnel based on modern educational trends. The implementation of tasks related to the training of highly qualified personnel, the establishment of effective cooperation in the practical implementation of innovative scientific achievements requires the training of modern-thinking, supportive of innovations, and comprehensively developed specialists in the education system.

Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026." This dissertation research, to a certain extent, serves the implementation of the tasks defined in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-60 "On Measures for the Further Improvement of the System of Training Qualified Personnel in Vocational Education and the Implementation of International Educational Programs" dated October 16, 2024, No. UP-158 "On Measures for the Further Improvement of the System of Training Qualified Personnel in Vocational Education and the Implementation of International Educational Programs" dated October 8, 2019, No. UP-5847 "On Approving the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030," as well as other regulatory legal documents adopted in this area.

Training highly qualified teachers who meet modern requirements is the main requirement of the international labor market today. They are the driving forces of society's development, which, in turn, creates the need to update the content of continuous education, innovative forms and methods of teaching, modern information and communication technologies, and the widespread introduction of advanced foreign experience in teaching, which serve to develop the professional competence of teachers. On this basis, a number of measures are being implemented today to improve the quality of education in educational institutions, to ensure the interconnectedness and continuity of educational stages.

Also, the development of professional competence of pedagogical personnel, the use of modern advanced foreign experience in the field, equipping them with professional knowledge, skills, and abilities, the independent creative use of scientific and technical

innovations, and the development of skills to solve promising tasks are considered important tasks.

Special attention should be paid to the professional competence of teachers and their analytical skills. Professional competence, professional self-awareness, respect for professional values, and career guidance are generalizing concepts that are one of the components of universal human culture, manifested in the example of professional formation, support, and development of innate abilities of the younger generation.

Today, the formation of a teacher's professional competence consists in increasing their daily competence and the effectiveness of their work. Training of qualified specialists is possible through the study and solution of problems related to the formation of professional skills in work, the formation of professional training.

The need to improve the pedagogical and psychological knowledge of future teachers is justified by the growth of social requirements for the educational institution and teachers. Not every teacher is just a teaching aid. Some teachers find it difficult to deviate even slightly from the traditional, established form of teaching. Any deviation from the norm can exclude the teacher from the educational process, and without this component, it is known that teaching is impossible. The innovative potential of the teacher is the key to the active and successful formation of innovative processes in the educational institution. So, how can we train a specialist who can work with traditional and innovative teaching methods?

Self-education, self-education, self-determination, and other special training are the result of the teacher's professional training. This preparation ensures the effectiveness of all work and is a regulatory element. One of the main qualities of a teacher, which is the key to professional skill, is readiness for innovative activity.

Innovations in the field of pedagogy, like any other innovations, create certain problems, since they cannot always be combined with classical teaching methods. This requires the introduction of fundamentally new pedagogical developments and methods. However, it is also necessary to consider the adaptation of the innovation itself to the new environment. Often, problems arise in the implementation of innovations designed for purposes other than other fields and intended to solve problems that are not part of the field of pedagogy. Such implementation leads to a distortion of the original meaning of the innovation and, as a result, causes dissatisfaction and disappointment with the use.

Successful introduction of innovations into the educational process is possible only if the teacher is able to assess the practical significance not only at the professional, but also at the personal level. However, practice shows that often a teacher is forced to engage in innovative activity without taking into account their professional training. At this stage of the research, it is necessary to define the concept of "teacher readiness for innovative activity." The definition of this concept, given by V.A. Slastenin and L.S. Podimova, is one of the most widespread, according to which "the teacher's readiness for innovative activity is openness, accessibility to something other than their own opinion.

Summarizing all of the above, it can be concluded that the concept of "readiness of a higher education teacher for innovative activity" implies a holistic new formation of the teacher's personality, including the ability for creativity and reflection, a motivational-value attitude to professional activity, stimulating innovative activity, regardless of experience or skill. This readiness represents a certain professional-pedagogical position that stimulates

innovative activity and effectively influences it. Often, the most common problem of teachers working with innovations is low innovative competence.

Innovative competence is a set of knowledge, skills, abilities, and certain personal qualities of a teacher that ensure special effectiveness in working with new pedagogical technologies. The components that make up preparation innovations are the teacher's interest in introducing innovations into the educational process, the ability to timely monitor and study current trends in education, as well as the ability to apply them in practice.

When introducing innovations into the educational process, it can be observed that the obligations to the teacher regarding theoretical knowledge, as well as practical skills, have significantly increased. In this case, the teacher should form the educational process in a student-centered manner, while also providing them with opportunities for independent work and self-development.

Important criteria for a teacher in implementing innovations in the educational process are:

- confidence in one's abilities, respect for the student's personality, mutual trust;
- understanding the inner world of the student, the ability to accept the student's position,
- cooperation (improvement of the educational process together with the student);
- dialogism, cooperation of the subjects of the educational process;
- the ability to express one's opinion, to defend one's position;

Although the teacher can comply with all the above criteria, he cannot be sure that he is ready for innovative activity.

Thus, we can conclude that another important component in preparing teachers for innovative activity is the mechanisms of adaptability. Based on this condition, we decide to modernize the optimization approach. We consider this approach as a component that contributes to the development of innovative activity in the education system as a whole, as well as in the thinking and activity of teachers. The optimization approach allows us to balance current pedagogical trends and the personal interaction of teachers with innovations.

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